

PolarFront Cruise

15-28 August 2023

RV Helmer Hanssen

Cruise report

Edited and compiled by Malin Daase

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Introduction

This expedition of the NRC funded project “*Polar Front ecosystem studies using novel autonomous technologies: Knowledge for environmental management and assessing ecological risk*” (PolarFront) elucidated the hydrographical, chemical and biological processes in the Barents Sea Polar Front region specifically during summer. After a successful spring mission in 2022, identical approaches were used to characterise the food web from bacterial activities to fish stomach contents. Financial support for this expedition was provided by the NRC, UiT, Conoco Philips, and Equinor.

The summer months in the Barents Sea see a major shift in biological processes compared to spring. While the spring season was characterized by massive diatom spring blooms and sea ice cover north of the Polar Front, the ice-free summer Barents Sea has lower primary production, often dominated by different dominant protist taxa with e.g. very high contributions of dinoflagellates. Our August science mission took samples and produced data focusing on the biodiversity and biological activity at all trophic levels (from bacteria to fish) from relatively warm Atlantic water into the cold Arctic domain. The deployments of autonomous vehicles (one glider, one sail buoy, and one small research catamaran) extended the research area and allowed for higher spatial and temporal resolution and repeated data collections across the frontal zone.

The research vessel *Helmer Hanssen* left port in Tromsø early morning on August 15 and reached after a calm transit the first and most southerly and Atlantic water dominated sampling location at 75°N and 29°30' E on August 17. Sampling included water collections, various plankton nets and pelagic trawls. On the way north, a transect using the towed MVP system provided high resolution data on ocean temperature, salinity and biological properties, that allowed us to precisely locate the region with the strongest frontal gradients to occur between 77°15' N and 77°45' N. We extended the transect to 78°30' N to collect samples in Arctic waters and from there continued southwards along the 29°30' transect line again with spatial resolution of our main sampling stations between 7.5 to (frontal zone) 30nm. Between the main stations, short station using only CTD, FRRF and a combined sampling package including acoustics, LOPC and LISST sensors allowed fast collection of important physical and biological properties. In total, we achieved nine full stations covering the range from Atlantic to the Arctic with high resolution in the frontal zone. The scientific efforts concluded with the successful recovery of a glider in stormy seas late on August 25. Scientific operation continued with acoustic transects across the Polar Front until the morning of August 26. The cruise ended in Tromsø on August 28. The report provides an overview on sampling approaches and first scientific data of the various science teams on board.

We would like to thank the captain and crew of R/V *Helmer Hanssen* for outstanding support throughout the entire science mission.

Rolf Gradinger, UiT, cruise leader

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Study area and cruise summary

The cruise was conducted at the Barents Sea Polar front along a transect following approximately 29.5° E. The first full station (PF1) was located in Atlantic Water south of the front. From there we steamed northwards mapping the water column with a CTD and LOPC attached to the Moving Vessel Profiler (MVP). At ca. 78°N we encountered Arctic water masses throughout the water column and the northern most full sample station (PF2) was located here. We steamed a bit further north for a short station, but since the hydrography did not change much we decided to focus the sampling south of PF2. Stations PF3 to PF9 were distributed across the Front to resolve the frontal structure in greater detail.

The weather was overall quite good, with temperature around 4 degrees. The skies were generally overcast, but the sea was largely calm, except for one of the last days when we encountered strong winds from the west. There was no sea ice in the study area during the cruise.

15 August: The ship was loaded on the 14th, so we were able to leave Tromsø already at 9 am after everyone had been to border control at the Police station. It was mostly calm while steaming northwards through the fjords but the wind picked up a bit when we reached open waters.

Leaving Tromsø (Photo: M. Daase)

16 August: We steamed northwards, preparing labs and making a sampling plan. Overcast skies, relatively calm seas.

We reached the first station (PF1) late in the evening and started our sampling program, which we finished around 4 am the next morning.

17 August: We steamed northwards, mapping the Polar Front with the MVP.

Otto in mid-air (Photo: M. Daase)

18 August: We deployed the sea glider and the sail buoy in the earlier morning and continued northwards. In the afternoon, we started sampling at PF2 and finished by midnight. The sea was calm enough to deploy the Otter.

19 August: During the night, we steamed northwards and took a short station (consisting of vertical profiles with the CTD, LOPC and FRRF) at 78.5°N. Afterwards, we turned south and started the full sampling program at PF3 after breakfast. During the day, several dead gulls showed up on the front deck of *Helmer Hanssen*. The crew discarded the birds and the front deck was closed until further notice due to infections risk with

bird flu. In the evening, we sampled shorter stations on our way to the next full station.

Between 20 and 26 August, we followed a similar schedule every day: starting in the morning with a full station and a shorter sample program in the evening.

21 August: After finishing work at PF5, we steamed northwards in the evening to pick up the sea glider which had some technical problems. The glider was re-deployed later the next day.

The daily Tucker Trawl deployment (Photo: M. Daase)

24 August: In the morning, the crew picked up a discarded fishing net from the sea and brought in on deck. Entangled in it, we found a young, dead seal.

Ghost net with dead seal (Photo: M. Daase)

25 August: After finishing sampling at PF9, we steamed northwards across the front to pick up the sea glider and run another MVP transect. On our way north, we spotted a dead polar bear drifting in the sea. We managed to recover the sea glider at 23:00 despite strong winds from the west. We started the MVP transect, but unfortunately encountered problems with the MVP and weather conditions became unfavourable, so we had to abandon those plans.

More dead vertebrates (Photo: M. Daase)

26 August: We steamed south in rather rocky seas.

27 August: The sea was calmer and even the sun came out for a few moments. Packing and cleaning commenced, and we met in the afternoon to present preliminary results.

28 August: We arrived in Tromsø at 10 am in sunny and warm weather, and started to unload the boat. Border control was finalized by 11 am, and equipment was transported to UiT.

Figure 1: Map of study area and location of stations.

Figure 2: Ice conditions during cruise (cryo.met.no)

Figure 3: CTD profiles from the main stations taken with Seabird CTD

Research projects

MVP transect

Sünnje Basedow, UiT

The Moving Vessel Profiler (MVP) was deployed to collect data with high-spatial resolution along our transect crossing the front. Instruments contained in the profiling unit ("fish") of the winch were a CTD (AML μ CTD), a fluorescence sensor (WETLABS) and a laser optical plankton counter (LOPC). The fluorescence sensor was calibrated against filtered chlorophyll samples at our main stations, see below. Together the instruments yield data on the physical environment, phytoplankton, zooplankton and other particle distributions (WP1). Combining these high-resolution data with formulas derived from ecological theory we can estimate secondary production and vital rates (WP2). Along the transect also ADCP data were collected and using those in connection to the LOPC-CTD-F data we can estimate flux across the front (WP1). During the cruise, the data provided by the MVP allowed to decide station positioning across the front based on a detailed picture of water mass and plankton distributions.

During the entire deployment of the MVP, weather conditions were optimal with very low wind speeds and calm sea. Apart from one stop at the surface due to a fishing vessel in our transect (20 min stop), no sampling issues whatsoever were experienced. A few breaks along the transect were taken to collect water samples and to set out the Sailbuoy and Seaglider.

Transect start: 75° N, 29°30' E, 17th August at 02:13 UTC

Transect end: 78° N, 29°30' E, 18th August at 11:09 UTC

In total the transect was 333 km long and 382 profiles to 25 m above bottom were collected, resulting in a spatial resolution of, on average, 1 profile every 870 m.

MVP-CTD data processing

Data from the AML μ CTD are directly fed into the LOPC data file. While the CTD logs data in 4 Hz, the LOPC logs in 2 Hz. To match up data resolution, CTD data were averaged to 2 Hz. Salinity will be calibrated against salinity from the ship's CTD once that one is calibrated against measured values in the Saliniograph at UiT.

Calibration of the MVP fluorometer

When the MVP winch is not profiling, no fluorescence data are written into the LOPC data file, therefore the fluorescence sensor can't be calibrated against filtered water samples while it is mounted in the MVP "fish". That's why at most main stations (PF 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8) the MVP fluorescence sensor was connected to the "Frankenstein" CTD and water collected by the ship's main CTD Niskin bottles (from 5, 10, Chl max, 50 and 100 m) was run through the sensor using a calibration cap and tubes. The MVP-LOPC logs fluorescence as raw value in mV, while the Frankenstein CTD during profiling is set to sample in engineer units (output format 'converted decimals' in the Seaterm software). Prior to calibration, the "Frankenstein" CTD was, therefore, set to output format 'raw decimal', which is in Volt. Data from each water depth were logged for ca. 1 min using the 'Capture' function in Seaterm and were averaged thereafter using a python routine. Finally, chlorophyll *a* concentrations obtained from the Phytoplankton group were plotted against averaged values from the calibration process and a linear regression was fitted to the data. The resulting equation was applied to all MVP fluorescence data (MVP fluorescence divided by 1000 to convert from mV to V):

Chl *a* concentration in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1} = 17.76 * (\text{MVP fluorescence} / 1000) - 0.48$ ($n = 30$, $r^2 = 0.91$)

LOPC data processing and quality control

The laser optical plankton counter counts and sizes particles in the size range of ca. 300 μm to 3 mm equivalent spherical diameter (ESD), which corresponds approximately to a range from larger copepod nauplii to adult krill. In addition, for larger particles (> ca. 6-800 μm ESD), the LOPC yields data on the shape and transparency of particles. Based on those features larger particles (MEPs) can be

distinguished and marine snow and zooplankton can be identified (Checkley et al. 2008, Schultes & Lopes 2009, Basedow et al. 2013, Trudonowska et al. 2014). For smaller particles this is not possible but methods have been developed to estimate the contribution of marine snow to smaller particles based on features of larger particles alone (Espinasse et al. 2018). LOPC data were processed and quality-controlled on-board using especially developed python scripts and following the steps outlined in Basedow et al. (2014). All collected data were of good quality, with few faulty MEPs and a low number of MEPs in general (cf. Schultes & Lopes 2009). Using the indicators developed by Espinasse et al. (2018), it appears that the LOPC along the entire region predominantly counted zooplankton and no marine snow or other particles (Table 1).

Table 1. *Quality control and particle assessment of MVP-LOPC data. TC = total count, AI = attenuation index, ESD = equivalent spherical diameter, MEP = multi element particle.*

#MEPs	% MEPs	TC/MEPs	Mean AI	Mean ESD	#Faulty	%Faulty	AI<0.2?	%MEPS <2?	Plankton and particle composition
77152	1.00	101	0.18	0.74	6	0.000	yes	yes	All files:
108866	1.06	95	0.15	0.62	8	0.000	yes	yes	Low detritus,
131146	1.24	82	0.13	0.58	11	0.000	yes	yes	if high chla
58281	1.24	82	0.13	0.58	7	0.000	yes	yes	PP colonies or
94421	1.04	97	0.14	0.61	8	0.000	yes	yes	chains
57839	1.05	96	0.12	0.57	8	0.000	yes	yes	
109870	1.06	95	0.12	0.56	10	0.000	yes	yes	
101816	1.00	101	0.13	0.58	7	0.000	yes	yes	
26385	0.83	121	0.15	0.65	0	0.000	yes	yes	
50912	0.98	103	0.15	0.67	2	0.000	yes	yes	
68841	1.01	100	0.12	0.57	11	0.000	yes	yes	
89938	1.16	87	0.12	0.57	11	0.000	yes	yes	
112534	1.26	80	0.14	0.63	11	0.000	yes	yes	
54335	1.63	63	0.17	0.79	5	0.000	yes	yes	
35593	1.35	75	0.19	0.93	3	0.000	yes	yes	
21581	1.39	73	0.18	0.99	4	0.000	yes	yes	
26092	1.38	73	0.18	1.00	9	0.000	yes	yes	
26518	1.10	92	0.19	0.87	4	0.000	yes	yes	
30131	1.48	69	0.19	0.93	14	0.000	yes	yes	
36551	1.38	73	0.19	0.79	3	0.000	yes	yes	
16198	1.40	73	0.20	0.77	2	0.000	yes	yes	

Results

Figure 4. Distribution across the polar front. Top: Temperature (°C), 2nd from top: Chlorophyll a concentration (µg L⁻¹), 3rd from top: Salinity (psu), bottom: older stages of *Calanus* spp. (ind. m⁻³) counted by LOPC. Small ticks on the top axis indicate profiles taken by the MVP, longer ticks indicate stations. Main stations are numbered, in-between stations are marked as '*'.

The Front was clearly captured by our sampling with high spatial resolution with the MVP and was located at 77.25° N latitude. A rough identification of water masses based on Sundfjord et al. (2020) indicates the following: In the very south of the transect, Atlantic Water was found, while the water mass that was most prevalent south of the front was Warm Polar Water ($S < 34.9$, $T > 0^{\circ}\text{C}$), likely originating from a mixture of Polar Water ($T < 0^{\circ}\text{C}$) and Atlantic Water ($S > 34.9$). North of the polar front Warm Polar Water was found in the surface, here the Polar Water might have been warmed up by solar radiation, and at depth, while Cold Barents Sea Dense Water ($T < -1.1^{\circ}\text{C}$) was prevalent in the layer between ca. 50 and ca. 150 m. A more detailed analysis of water mass distribution will be carried out on land, once the salinity sensor is properly calibrated.

Chlorophyll *a* concentrations along the transect were low, mostly $< 2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, and very low north of the front. Also *Calanus* concentrations were relatively low and mostly confined to the lower part of the water column.

Vertical sampling at stations with LOPC, LISST and WBAT

Sünnje Basedow, Einat Sandbank

The vertical sampling at the stations complements the high-resolution sampling along the transect. Not the least, by adding the LISST (IOPAS, Emilia Trudnowska) to the sampling platform ("Frankenstein", Fig. 5) we can collect data for calculating biovolume spectra (WP2) from sizes from 1 μm to 3 mm ESD (LISST 1-300 μm , LOPC 0.3-3 mm) and will evaluate the possibility to expand that size range further to larger sizes (WBAT) and to smaller sizes (flow cytometry). At the stations we sampled three vertical profiles, which yields a higher statistic certainty than just one profile so that vertical distributions are more likely to reflect real distributions. Not all instruments worked on all stations, due to water intrusions in some cables that connected the different instruments, but all in all we collected a good data set across the Polar Front.

Figure 5: "Frankenstein" – rosette with CTD, LOPC, LISST and WBAT (Photo: S. Basedow)

Table 2. Deployments and data availability of "Frankenstein"

Ship ID	St.	Sampling	LOPC	LISST	WBAT	CTD-F
1097	PF1	3 profiles to 300 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1120	PF2	40 min at 45 m	no	no	yes*	no
1127	PF2	3 profiles to 300 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1132	PFx	3 profiles to 220 m	no	yes	yes	no**
1141	PF3	40 min at 35 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1142	PF3	20 min at 35 m, 20 min at 20 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1148	PF3	3 profiles to 210 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1152	PF3.5	3 profiles to 190 m	yes*	yes*	yes*	no
1160	PF4	45 min at 35 m	no	no	yes	no
1161	PF4	45 min at 35 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1168	PF4	3 profiles to 170 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1181	PF5	30 min at 80 m, 30 min at 30 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1186	PF5	3 profiles to 175 m	no	yes	yes	no**
1190	PF3b	3 profiles to 220 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1191	PF3.5b	2 profiles to 190 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1193	PF4.5b	3 profiles to 175 m	no	yes	yes	no**
1194	PF5b	3 profiles to 174 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1197	PF5.5	3 profiles to 172 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1207	PF6	35 min at 100 m, 35 min at 50 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1216	PF6	3 profiles to 190 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1222	PF6.3	3 profiles to 190 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1225	PF6.6	3 profiles to 200 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1234	PF7	30 min at 35 m, 20 min at 70 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1240	PF7	3 profiles to 220 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1245	PF7.3	3 profiles to 240 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1248	PF7.6	3 profiles to 240 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1255	PF8	30 min at 45 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1259	PF8	3 profiles to 245 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1264	PF8.25	3 profiles to 250 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1267	PF8.5	3 profiles to 256 m	only 150 m	yes	yes	no**
1270	PF8.75	3 profiles to 260 m	yes	yes	yes	yes
1277	PF9	25 min at 220 m, 25 min at 180 m	yes	no	yes	yes
1282	PF9	3 profiles to 265 m	yes	yes	yes	yes

* No depth data for deployment available

** CTD-F data were scrambled somehow due to malfunction of the LOPC. Some information can be extracted from the scrambled data.

"Frankenstein" data processing

CTD, FLU, LISST and LOPC

CTD data were processed as described for the MVP sampling, and so were LOPC data. The fluorometer was tried to calibrate in a similar way than described for the MVP but only data from one station (PF9) were available ($n = 5$), and these did not yield sufficient data for calibration. The fluorometer on the UPC will therefore remain uncalibrated for this cruise. LISST data were pre-processed using Sequoia LISST software and will be further analysed ashore. Data collected by the LOPC when it was mounted on "Frankenstein" were of good quality, with few faulty MEPs and a low number of MEPs in general (ref. MVP section). According to the indicators, detritus and marine snow were not prevalent, and the LOPC counted mostly zooplankton, with larger copepods contributing significantly at many stations (Table 3).

Table 3. Quality control and particle assessment of MVP-LOPC data. TC = total count, AI = attenuation index, ESD = equivalent spherical diameter, MEP = multi element particle.

Ship Log	#MEPs	% MEPs	TC/MEPs	Mean AI	Mean ESD	#Faulty	%Faulty	AI<0.2?	%MEP S <2?	Plankton and particle composition
1097	21492	3.47	29.7	0.27	1.41	119	0.006	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1127	6366	2.42	42.5	0.24	1.25	5	0.001	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1148	5367	1.99	51.0	0.23	1.09	1	0.000	no	yes	Clear water, LOPC mainly counting ZP
1168	18163	3.18	32.5	0.26	1.55	25	0.002	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1190	7970	2.63	39.0	0.23	1.55	11	0.001	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1191	9469	4.01	26.0	0.28	1.57	30	0.003	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1194	8463	3.21	32.2	0.25	1.58	32	0.004	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1197	7072	2.30	44.5	0.25	1.26	8	0.001	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1216	6583	2.26	45.3	0.24	1.09	15	0.002	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1222	7729	2.18	47.0	0.28	1.47	28	0.004	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1225	4507	1.15	87.9	0.22	0.92	2	0.000	no	yes	Clear water, LOPC mainly counting ZP
1240	9768	2.32	44.1	0.21	1.10	7	0.001	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1245	4001	1.31	77.2	0.19	0.76	0	0.000	yes	yes	Low detritus, if high chla PP colonies or chains
1248	6337	1.67	60.9	0.24	1.39	20	0.003	no	yes	Clear water, LOPC mainly counting ZP
1259	5240	1.57	64.6	0.24	1.13	15	0.003	no	yes	Clear water, LOPC mainly counting ZP
1264	4838	1.32	76.8	0.23	0.91	0	0.000	no	yes	Clear water, LOPC mainly counting ZP
1267	1603	1.84	55.2	0.17	1.23	1	0.001	yes	yes	Low detritus, if high chla PP colonies aor chains
1270	5366	1.59	63.9	0.24	1.20	3	0.001	no	yes	Clear water, LOPC mainly counting ZP
1277	4865	3.05	33.8	0.26	1.40	11	0.002	no	no	Plankton dominated by big copepods
1282	7765	1.96	52.1	0.30	1.40	39	0.005	no	yes	Clear water, LOPC mainly counting ZP

Results

Figure 6. Vertical distribution of older stages of *Calanus* spp. as identified by LOPC (black bars) in relation to salinity (blue), temperature (red, °C) and fluorescence (green). Left: station PF9, centre: station PF6 (front), right: station PF3.

First analyses of the vertical LOPC data show that *Calanus* copepods were distributed gradually deeper across the front, and stayed in the deepest part of the water column south of the front, indicating overwintering there (Figure 6).

Acoustic probe (WBAT)

We deployed an acoustic probe composed of a Wideband Acoustic Transceiver (WBAT; Kongsberg Maritime AS) mounted on the LOPC rosette frame and connected to a kHz split beam transducer (Model ES38-18DK; 36-45 kHz) and a 333 kHz single beam transducer (Model ES333-7CDK-single; 280-380 kHz), both operated in broadband mode split-beam wideband (Figure 7). Deployments were either stationary at set depth and time intervals where only acoustic and CTD data was collected, or as part of the multi-instrument deployment to profile the water column (Table 4). Stationary deployments were predominantly side-facing but at Station PF5 the transducers were remounted to face downwards. At the stationary sites, ping rate was set to 1 second, range to 100 m, pulse length to 2,048 μ s, and power to 450 W at 38kHz and 50 W at 333 kHz. Data was collected in highspeed mode only at stationary sites. During profile deployments ping rate was set to 1 second, range to 50 m, pulse length to 2,048 μ s, and power to 450 W at 38kHz and 50 W at 333 kHz. The WBAT was calibrated in January 2022. For most deployment the internal time of the WBAT was synchronized with the LOPC-CTD to extract the exact depth at each ping in post processing. When the timing was not synchronized, the difference in times was noted for correction (Table 4).

Table 4: All WBAT deployments and the settings used. Red cell color indicates deployments where some equipment did not record.

Date (UTC)	Station	Boat ID	Duration	Type	# of Profiles	Data Mode	Direction	Comments	Time Correction
8/16/2023	PF1	1097	0:53:00	Profile	3	Normal	Side	Pulled out and restarted after first drop, pinging weird but working?	y, 2 hours
8/18/2023	PF2	1120	0:54:14	Stationary	1	Fast	side	Held at 40 m at stratification	y, 2 hours
8/18/2023	PF2	1127	0:48:08	Profile	3	Normal	side		y, 2 hours
8/19/2023	PFx	1132	0:33:27	Profile	3	Normal	side		y, 2 hours
8/19/2023	PF3	1141	0:51:16	Stationary	1	Fast	side	Held at 35 m at stratification, turned of ADCP	y, 2 hours
8/19/2023	PF3	1142	0:24:44	Stationary	1	Normal	side	Held at 20m for 20 min and 35 for 20 min, turned off ADCP	y, 2 hours
8/19/2023	PF3	1148	0:38:14	Profile	3	Normal	side	1 second delay on WBAT, no LOPC or LISST	y, 2 hours and one second delay
8/19/2023	PF3.5	1152	0:33:36	Profile	3	Normal	side	No depth	y, 2 hours
8/20/2023	PF4	1160	0:53:36	Stationary	1	Fast	side	Held at 35m, ADCP not turned off, 1024 ping duration	y, 2 hours
8/20/2023	PF4	1161	0:52:02	Stationary	1	Fast	side	Held at 35m, ADCP not turned off, 2048 ping duration	n
8/20/2023	PF4	1168	1:09:07	Profile	3	Normal	side	Started at 12:01	n
8/21/2023	PF5	1181	1:12:38	Stationary	1	Fast	Down	30 min at 80m 30 min at 30m, brought up to 30m at 10:19:48 UTC	y, one second delay
8/21/2023	PF5	1186	0:30:53	Profile	3	Normal	side	One second delay	y, one second delay
8/21/2023	PF3B	1190	0:45:59	Profile	3	Normal	side	One second delay	y, one second delay
8/21/2023	PF3.5B	1191	0:28:14	Profile	2	Normal	side	One second delay, forgot to click UTC box	y, one second delay. Maybe also 2 hours
8/21/2023	PF4.5	1193	0:34:44	Profile	3	Normal	side		n
8/21/2023	PF5	1194	0:39:52	Profile	3	Normal	side	Started at 23:06 but winch cable snapped	n
8/22/2023	PF5.5	1197	0:35:37	Profile	3	Normal	side		n
8/22/2023	PF6	1207	0:40:30	Stationary	1	Fast	side	Stationary at 50m then 100m	n
8/22/2023	PF6	1216	0:33:08	Profile	3	Normal	Side		n
8/22/2023	PF6.3	1222	0:34:09	Profile	3	Normal	Side		n
8/22/2023	PF6.6	1225	0:37:40	Profile	3	Normal	Side		n
8/23/2023	PF7	1234	0:57:30	Stationary	1	Fast	Side	Held at 35 for 30 min, dropped to 70m for 20 min dropped at 09 56:16	y, 2 second delay
8/23/2023	PF7	1240	0:38:03	Profile	3	Normal	Side		y, 1 second delay
8/23/2023	PF7.3	1245	0:40:42	profile	3	Normal	Side		n
8/23/2023	PF7.6	1248	0:46:34	profile	3	Normal	Side		n
8/24/2023	PF8	1255	0:41:13	Stationary	1	Fast	Side		n
8/24/2023	PF8	1259	0:40:02	profile	3	Normal	Side		y, 1 second ahead
8/24/2023	PF8.25	1264	0:39:52	profile	3	Normal	Side		n
8/24/2023	PF8.5	1267	1:20:33	profile	3	Normal	Side		n
8/24/2023	PF8.75	1270	0:37:32	profile	3	Normal	Side		n
8/25/2023	PF9	1277	1:10:58	Stationary	1	Fast	Side	25 min at 220, 25min 180, change at	y, 2 second delay
8/25/2023	PF9	1282	0:43:09	Profile	3	Fast	Side		y 1 second delay

Acoustic analyses

Acoustic data will be examined and cleaned with Echoview® 13.1. WBAT acoustic profiles recorded will be calibrated to account for the change of sound speed with depth based on data collected by the Seabird 911 Plus CTD®. The CTD's logged temperature, salinity, and sound speed (Chen and Millero, 1977), will be used to derive the coefficient of absorption at each frequency (Francois and Garrison, 1982). When necessary Echoview's algorithms will be used to remove background noise, and impulse noise (De Robertis and Higginbottom, 2007; Ryan et al., 2015). A minimum signal to noise ratio threshold of 10 dB will be applied. Samples with a lower signal to noise ratio are considered indistinguishable from background noise and excluded from the analysis with the background noise algorithm.

Preliminary results.

Due to the large amount of post processing required for accurate interpretation of data collected by the WBAT (stationery and profiles), results are preliminary and qualitative only.

- 1) WBAT profiles show acoustic backscatter decreased with increasing Latitude for 38 kHz. Stations North of the Polar Front had acoustic backscatter concentrated in deep water both in 38 kHz and 333kHz (Figure 7).

Figure 7. WBAT echograms from three sites across the Polar Front.

- 2) A dramatic difference between stations PF6 and PF6.3 was recorded by the WBAT at 38kHz (Figure 8). At 333kHz there does not seem to be as dramatic of a difference, but quantitative scrutinizing of data will be completed at a later time.

Figure 8. WBAT echograms from station PF6 and PF6.3.

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Water sampling, phytoplankton and production rate measurements

Christien Laber, Emma Forss, Victoria Eggen and Eva Leu

The Phytoplankton group collected water samples from the Niskin bottles attached to the rosette with the Conductivity, Temperature and Depth (CTD) sensor. These samples are analysed for various parameters including Chlorophyll a (Chl-a), Particulate Organic Carbon/Nitrogen (POC/PON), taxonomy, flow cytometry, nutrients, Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC), and maximum photosynthetic yield determined by Fast Repetition Rate fluorometry (FRRf). The CTD sampling was performed in two casts at each station, the first collecting water from close to the bottom, depth of maximum in situ Chl a fluorescence and 5 m. The second cast was used to collect water from 100, 50, and 10 m depth. Depending on the nature of water parameters and protocols, some of the water samples from the Niskin bottles at each CTD station were directly collected in labelled bottles and tubes, i.e. Chl a, POC, Taxonomy, while those parameters that are analysed in dissolved state were first filtered to remove particulate material and then stored in the labelled bottles, for example, nutrients and DOC. Among the list of variables shown in Table 5, only Chl a was analyzed onboard. The remaining samples were stored frozen (or cooled) and will be processed later at UiT – The Arctic University of Norway. Further details are provided in the methodology section.

Table 5. Overview of the water parameters measured with their procedures, storage and importance.

Variable	Filter	Container	Storage	Importance
Chl-a	GF/F (25 mm)	Polycarbonate vials; 5ml 90% acetone	4°C; dark for 12-24 hours prior to extraction	Serves as proxy for phytoplankton biomass
Nutrients	Burnt GF/F (25 mm), Swinnex, syringe	15 ml Falcon tube	-20°C; dark	Concentrations of inorganic macronutrients available in the water
Taxonomy 200 ml	None	Brown glass bottle (200 mL; 1% formaldehyde (5 mL), buffered with Hexamin	4°C; dark	Microscopic analysis of phytoplankton species composition.
Flow Cytometry	None	4 ml cryovials, 20 µL of glutaraldehyde	-80°C; Ziploc	Number and size of cells in a water sample. Differentiate algal and bacteria.
POC/PON	Burnt GF/F (25 mm)	Burnt tinfoil pocket;	-20°C	Content of carbon and nitrogen in particulate organic material
DOC	Burnt GF/F (25 mm), Swinnex, syringe	HCl addition	4°C; dark	Dissolved organic carbon in the water, potentially used by bacteria

Table 6: Overview of all water samples taken for different types of analyses and incubations during the cruise

Water samples overview															
x: replicate (from field sample)															
station	date	depth	event #	Samples taken							Activity measurements (incubations)				
				Chl a	POC/PON	13C/15N	Nutrients	DIC*	flow cytometry	taxonomy	sample for LOPC calibration	14C primary production	bacterial production	mixotrophy	FRRF
PF1	16/08/2023	5	1085	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x	x	
	16/08/2023	10	1091	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	16/08/2023	Chla max	1085	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x		
	16/08/2023	50	1091	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				(x)
	16/08/2023	100	1091	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	16/08/2023	bottom	1085	xxx	xxx		xxx			x					
PF2	18/08/2023	5	1111	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x	x	x
	18/08/2023	10	1117	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	18/08/2023	Chla max	1111	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x		x
	18/08/2023	50	1117	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	18/08/2023	100	1117	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	18/08/2023	bottom	1111	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					
PF3	19/08/2023	5	1133	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x	x	x
	19/08/2023	10	1140	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	19/08/2023	Chla max	1133	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x		x
	19/08/2023	50	1140	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	19/08/2023	100	1140	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	19/08/2023	bottom	1133	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					
PF4	20/08/2023	5	1153	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x	x	x
	20/08/2023	10	1159	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	20/08/2023	Chla max	1153	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x		x
	20/08/2023	50	1159	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	20/08/2023	100	1159	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	20/08/2023	bottom	1153	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					
PF5	21/08/2023	5	1173	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x		x
	21/08/2023	10	1180	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	21/08/2023	Chla max	1173	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x		x
	21/08/2023	50	1180	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	21/08/2023	100	1180	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	21/08/2023	bottom	1173	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					
PF6	22/08/2023	5	1199	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x	x	x
	22/08/2023	10	1206	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	22/08/2023	Chla max	1199	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x		x
	22/08/2023	50	1206	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	22/08/2023	100	1206	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	22/08/2023	bottom	1199	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					
PF6.3	22/08/2023	Chla max	1220	xxx	xxx				xx	x					x
PF7	23/08/2023	5	1226	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x		x	x	x	x
	23/08/2023	10	1233	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					x
	23/08/2023	Chla max	1226	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x		x	x		x
	23/08/2023	50	1233	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					x
	23/08/2023	100	1233	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					
	23/08/2023	bottom	1226	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					
PF8	24/04/2023	5	1249	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x	x			x	x
	24/04/2023	10	1254	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	24/04/2023	Chla max	1249	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x	x				x
	24/04/2023	50	1254	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	24/04/2023	100	1254	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	24/04/2023	bottom	1249	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x					
PF9	25/04/2023	5	1271	xxx	xxx		xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x	x	x
	25/04/2023	10	1276	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	25/04/2023	Chla max	1271	xxx	xxx	xxxx	xxx	x	xx	x	x	x	x		x
	25/04/2023	50	1276	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				x
	25/04/2023	100	1276	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx	x	x				
	25/04/2023	bottom	1271	xxx	xxx		xxx		xx						

Chlorophyll-a

Water samples for chlorophyll-a measurements were taken at defined depths using a Niskin bottle rosette. A vacuum pump system and glass microfiber papers with a mesh size of 0.7 µm were used for filtering the samples, and the volume of water (Table 6) necessary for acquisition of sufficient amounts of chlorophyll was filtered. Two replicates of each sample were processed for the station PF1, and for the remaining stations three replicates per sample were processed. After filtration, filter papers were removed with a forceps and deposited in individually labelled plastic tubes inside a fridge for chlorophyll-a extraction in 5 mL of 90% acetone overnight.

Following overnight extraction, samples were taken out of the fridge appx. 15 minutes before fluorescence measurements to attain room temperature. Fluorescence measurements were carried out using a fluorometer and a fluorometric acidification method. Each acetone solution was transferred to a glass cuvette by pouring and placed in the fluorometer, after which the fluorometer readout in volts was noted. Subsequently, the cuvette was taken out of the instrument and 2 drops of 5% HCl was added, followed by covering of the cuvette opening with a piece of clean parafilm and gentle mixing. The sample was then placed back in the fluorometer and the new readout was written down. This process was repeated for each sample and replicate.

Chla measurements onboard with a Turner fluorometer (picture from previous cruise).

Preliminary results of chlorophyll-a measurements

Generally, the chlorophyll-a fluorescence values indicated that the primary producers were mostly present in the uppermost 25-30m, above a very strong thermo- (and often as well halo-) cline. Below the stratified layer, Chl a concentrations decreased rapidly down to 0.1 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ or less. Chl a concentrations ranged from < 0.1 to almost 2.1 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$, with a peak in the vertical distribution most often around 25m depth (see Table 7, Figure 8). Phaeophytin values were generally high, probably affected by the high grazing activity. The relatively seen high Chl a concentration measured at 100m depth at PF7 must be an error and will be removed from the dataset. No peak at 100m depth was visible on the continuous in situ fluorescence profiles at this station.

Table 7: Depth of maximum Chl a concentrations at all sampling stations

PF1	PF2	PF3	PF4	PF5	PF6	PF6.3	PF7	PF8	PF9
20m	40m	25m	27m	22m	25m	25m	25m	25m	17.5m

Figure 8. Chlorophyll-a concentrations measured from water samples taken at six depths at each station.

The amount of Chl a integrated over the entire water column (based on the concentration measurements from 6 distinct depths) ranged from 22 to 68 mg Chl a m⁻² (Figure 9), with the three stations sampled first showing the lowest, and the last station (PF9) the highest concentrations.

Figure 9: Depth-integrated Chl a at all sampling stations, calculated from the discrete measurements.

Nutrients

The water samples were directly taken with a sterile syringe and vinyl gloves to avoid contamination from the Niskin bottles for nutrients. A Swinnex filter holder with a burnt GF/F (25mm) filter was attached to the acid-washed syringe. After rinsing the filter and the containers, the water was then filtered

in three replicates into 15 ml centrifuge tubes for each depth, respectively. The samples were then stored at -20°C until further analysis on return to land.

Taxonomy

For species composition analysis samples were collected from the CTD. From each depth, 200 ml of water was filled into a labelled brown glass bottle. 5 ml of formaldehyde (and some hexamine as a buffer) was added to each sample and stored in darkness at 4°C for later analysis on land.

Flow Cytometry

Water samples will be the measurement for bacteria and algae abundance using Flow Cytometry. In preparation for this, duplicates of each sample, one for bacteria and one for algae, were made ready. Two 5 ml cryovials were filled with 3.5-4 ml of a sample before adding 20 µL of glutaraldehyde (25% or higher) in each tube. Samples were then frozen at -80°C.

POC/PON

At each station for the POC measurements, the collected water from the CTD for each depth was filtered in three replicates through burned GF/F (25mm) filters with the aid of a low vacuum pressure pump. The volume (1L) for each replicate and the time needed for filtering was noted down. The bottles and funnels were rinsed with filtered seawater after each sample. The filters were then folded and individually packed in burned tinfoil, packaged in plastic zip bags and stored at -20°C until analysis in the lab on return.

DIC

Total dissolved inorganic carbon measures the sum of bicarbonate, carbonate and carbonic acid and dissolved CO₂. Here DIC was taken as a reference measurement for spike and incubation measurements with C¹⁴; therefore, the samples were taken not directly from the Niskin bottle, but from the bulk sample that was prepared for these incubations. For DIC and the ¹⁴C incubation, seawater was taken from 5m and the depth corresponding to the chlorophyll maximum of each sampling station, respectively and filled into air-tight containers. To these exetainers, 20µl HgCl were added under strict safety standards. Each exetainer was then stored at 4°C in the dark until analysis on land.

Primary and bacterial production

By Emma Forss

Primary production and bacterial production were measured at 5 m and at the chlorophyll maximum at eight (P1-P7 and P9) and seven (P1-P4, P6-P7, and P9) out of the nine stations, respectively. Water samples from the rosette were collected into insulated containers, with all incubations started within three hours of collection.

Incubations in the isotope lab

Primary production

60 mL subsamples were measured into ten clear and two dark incubation flasks (*Corning*), with the latter containing di-chloromethyl urea. Each bottle was spiked with ^{14}C working solution ($4 \mu\text{Ci/mL}$) and incubated for three hours in temperature-controlled PI chambers before filtration onto GF/F (*Whatman*). The range of light intensities in the chambers were measured using a Walz four-pi microsensor. Temperatures were set to *in situ* as measured by the CTD, aside from PF1 where the incubation temperature was set at 1°C . Filters were acidified with 0.5N HCl and dried (48h) before addition of 10 mL Ecolume scintillation cocktail. Samples were transported to UiT for scintillation counting after the cruise. See Campbell et al. (2016) for details on incubation methodology.

Bacterial production

15 mL subsamples were measured into six sterile falcon tubes and spiked with ^3H -Leucine ($59 \mu\text{Ci/mL}$). Three samples were immediately killed with 50% trichloroacetic acid solution. Samples were incubated in darkness for six hours at *in situ* temperatures, aside from PF1 which was incubated at 1°C . After incubation the three remaining samples were killed with the 50% TCA solution, before filtration onto $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ cellulose acetate filters (*Whatman*). Filters were rinsed with 5% TCA and 80% ethanol, and dried (24h) before dissolution with ethyl acetate and addition of 10 mL Ecolume scintillation cocktail. Samples were transported to UiT for scintillation counting after the cruise.

Reference:

Campbell K, Mundy CJ, Landy JC, Delaforge A, Michel C, Rysgaard S (2016) Community dynamics of bottom-ice algae in Dease Strait of the Canadian Arctic. *Prog Oceanogr* 149:27-39

Phytoplankton photophysiology measured by Fast Repetition Rate fluorometry (FRRf)

By *Eva Leu*

In order to gain more detailed information about the physiological state of the different phytoplankton communities we encountered on the cruise, water samples from the Niskin bottles were taken for analysis by Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometry. This technique allows to measure in a controlled benchtop-approach maximum photosynthetic yield of dark-acclimated microalgae, which gives indications about potential stress. In addition, Fast Light Curves (FLC) were measured, which provide information about the photoacclimation state of algae.

These analyses were carried out at all 9 main sampling stations (PF1-PF6), usually from four different depths: 5-10-Chla max-50m.

Preliminary results show high yield values at most stations and depths, indicating well-growing algae in favourable conditions. Measurements at 50m depth were not always possible as the biomass was very low. FLC data need to be quality-checked and re-fitted before final results will be available.

In addition to measuring field samples from all stations, cross-incubation experiments were planned, similar to those carried out on the two previous May-cruises. However, a major challenge this time was a very high abundance of small grazers in all phytoplankton net samples that could not be separated from the phytoplankton community that itself showed a high contribution of mixotrophic species. During three attempts of carrying out experiments, photosynthetic yield decreased down to 0.2-0.25 in all treatments within 24 hours, regardless of the type of filtered seawater added. Therefore, no further experiments were carried out.

Figure 10: Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometer used for photophysiological measurements

The laboratory-based FRRf measurements will be compared to the continuous *in situ* profiles with another FRRf were carried out at multiple stations. Comparing those with the controlled measurements of dark-acclimated yield from discrete sampling depths will provide valuable information about the potential and limitations of applying this technique *in situ*.

Phytoplankton composition

Rolf Gradinger, UiT

The composition of larger phytoplankton (>20µm) was assessed based on one 20µm net plankton samples collected at each main station from 30m water depths to the surface. A small subsample (ca. 2.7ml) was filled into an Utermöhl chamber and analysed alive within 1.5 hours after sampling to provide first insights into species diversity with a Zeiss inverted microscope.

All samples were dominated by photo- and heterotrophic dinoflagellates. Common phytoplankton taxa included the genus *Ceratium* spp. and *Dinophysis norvegica*. The chrysophyte *Dinobryon baltica* occurred only in the northern half of the transect. Interestingly, diatoms were nearly absent in all samples, with regular occurrence only at stations P6 to P9. Here, cells of *Leptocylindrus danicus*, *Chaetoceros* spp. and *Rhizosolenia* spp. were seen in low abundances. No colonies of *Phaeocystis pouchetii* were observed, however this species might have occurred in the smaller size classes not sampled with the plankton net.

Thecate heterotrophic dinoflagellates including *Proto-peridinium* spp. dominated the heterotrophic fraction together with tintinnid ciliates. Abundances at the southerly stations P1 and P9 were so high that the plankton net sample appeared to be pink. Several metazoan taxa were also collected by the plankton net with rotatorians and *Microsetella norvegica* as common taxa.

In situ FRRF deployments

Rolf Gradinger, UiT

A downward looking FRRF (Chelsea, Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometer) was deployed at all main stations and the short intermittent stations. The FRRF was mounted in a frame together with a CASTAWAY CTD. Recordings were done ca every 0.5m depth over the uppermost 90m of the water column (for example see Figure 12). The recorded yield measurements were highest in the uppermost 40m of the water column reaching maximum values of 0.5. At stations collected with higher irradiance values quenching caused reduced yield values while at days of low irradiance, yield values were nearly constant in the upper mixed layer.

Further data exploration will include linking the ambient FRRF measurements with water column hydrography, in-situ irradiance, nutrient concentrations, algal diversity and the algal activity measurements using onboard FRRF and productivity incubations.

Mesozooplankton composition and *Calanus* lipid content

Malin Daase, Sinnje Basedow, Nicholas Gosset (UiT)

We used a number of different nets as well as optical sensors to determine the distribution patterns and species composition, abundance and biomass of the different size classes of the zooplankton community in the study area.

Copepods of the genus *Calanus* are key species in the energy transfer between primary producers and higher trophic levels and often dominate the mesozooplankton community in the Arctic and sub-Arctic Barents Sea. To estimate their production and lipid content, we measured egg production rates and measured the population lipid content in the study area.

Mesozooplankton species composition, abundance, biomass

To determine the mesozooplankton community composition, abundance and vertical distribution, a Multinet (MPS) (HydroBios Kiel, 180 μm , 0.25 m^2 opening area) was deployed at each main station. Samples were taken from 5 standard depth strata (bottom- 200-100-50-20-0 m) and fixed in 4% formalin in seawater solution. These samples will be analysed for community and *Calanus* stage composition at UiT. To estimate the biomass of the mesozooplankton community a WP2 net (HydroBios Kiel, 180 μm , 0.25 m^2 opening area) was taken from the entire water column. The sample was size fractionated into a 1000 μm and 180 μm fraction by pouring it through a 1000 and 180 μm sieve. Each sample was rinsed with fresh water and placed in a pre-weighted weighing dish and dried at 60°C in the drying oven. The dried samples were weighed back at UiT.

Table 8: Overview of Multinet samples

station number	location	Latitude	Longitude	bottom depth	date	sample depth
1092	PF1	75.00	29.42	367	16.08.2023	345-200-100-50-20-0
1121	PF2	78.00	29.31	326	18.08.2023	310-200-100-50-20-0
1143	PF3	77.72	29.51	223	19.08.2023	205-100-50-20-0
1162	PF4	77.52	29.42	189	20.08.2023	175-100-50-20-0
1182	PF5	77.36	29.36	182	21.08.2023	168-100-50-20-0
1208	PF6	77.23	29.40	191	22.08.2023	170-100-50-20-0
1235	PF7	76.99	29.48	236	23.08.2023	220-100-50-20-0
1256	PF8	76.74	29.52	254	24.08.2023	235-200-100-50-20-0
1278	PF9	76.32	29.58	275	25.08.2023	260-200-100-50-20-0

Calanus population lipid content

To estimate the lipid content of the *Calanus* community, two samples were taken with a WP2 (180 μm mesh size, 0.25 m^2 opening): one from ~10 m above sea floor to ca. 100 m above sea floor, and one from 50 m to surface. The samples were transferred into a measuring beaker and filled with filtered sea water to a known volume (200–600 ml, depending on density of the sample). Quantitative subsamples were taken with a 5 mL pipette with an enlarged opening and transferred into a petri dish. Digital images (lateral view) were taken of all *Calanus* (living and dead) in each subsample using a Leica stereomicroscope with a camera (Leica DFC420). Subsample size was chosen to contain at least 100 *Calanus* from each sample. Copepodite stage of each individual was determined while taking the pictures. The digital images were used to measure lipid sac area, prosome length and prosome area of specimens using ImageJ, an open source graphics program (Rasband 1997–2009). Lipid content of individual *Calanus* specimens was calculated from lipid sac area according to Vogedes et al. (2010).

Egg and faecal pellet production

We took additional samples with the WP2 and WP3 net to pick out individual *Calanus* females for egg and faecal pellet production incubations. To measure *Calanus* egg production, females of *Calanus* (around 20 individuals per species, if present) were placed in individual incubation chambers with false bottoms. The chambers were filled with filtered sea water and *Calanus* were incubated for 24 hours inside the cold room (~4°C). After 24 hours, the incubation was stopped by removing the individuals from the incubation chambers. Live individuals were photographed for subsequent lipid content

estimation. The number of eggs and fecal pellets produced in each chamber was counted under a stereomicroscope.

Egg incubations were only conducted at PF1 and PF2 were females were already rare. At the other stations we did not encounter any females in the samples. No eggs were produced at PF1 and PF2.

Table 9: Overview of WP2 samples taken

station number	location	date	sample depth (from)	sample depth (to)	purpose
1093	PF1	16.08.2023	365	0	biomass
1123	PF2	18.08.2023	315	0	biomass
1145	PF3	19.08.2023	191	0	biomass
1163	PF4	20.08.2023	175	0	biomass
1183	PF5	21.08.2023	170	0	biomass
1212	PF6	22.08.2023	190	0	biomass
1236	PF7	23.08.2023	225	0	biomass
1257	PF8	24.08.2023	245	0	biomass
1279	PF9	25.08.2023	265	0	biomass
1166	PF4	20.08.2023	50	20	community (replace Multinet sample)
1094	PF1	16.08.2023	360	200	lipid deep
1095	PF1	16.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface
1124	PF2	18.08.2023	315	200	lipid deep
1125	PF2	18.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface
1146	PF3	19.08.2023	195	150	lipid deep
1147	PF3	19.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface
1165	PF4	20.08.2023	175	100	lipid deep
1167	PF4	20.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface
1184	PF5	21.08.2023	170	100	lipid deep
1185	PF5	21.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface
1213	PF6	22.08.2023	190	100	lipid deep
1214	PF6	22.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface
1237	PF7	23.08.2023	225	100	lipid deep
1238	PF7	23.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface
1257	PF8	24.08.2023	245	200	lipid deep
1258	PF8	24.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface
1280	PF9	25.08.2023	265	200	lipid deep
1281	PF9	25.08.2023	50	0	lipid surface

Preliminary results

Calanus in the size range of *C. finmarchicus* dominated at the southern side of the front, while *C. glacialis* dominated in the north. The contribution and abundance of *C. hyperboreus* was overall low (Figure 13).

Figure 13: *Calanus* species composition along transect in deeper waters and at surface (f= *C. finmarchicus*, g= *C. glacialis*, h= *C. hyperboreus*)

South of the front (PF8, 9 and 1) and at the northern most station (PF2), older copepodites stages (CIV and CV) dominated, while at PF3-PF6 the *Calanus* population was dominated by young copepodites stages (CI-CIII) (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Abundance estimates and stage composition of *C. finmarchicus* (f) and *C. glacialis* in deeper waters and at surface.

Figure 15: Total lipid content of *C. finmarchicus* (f) and *C. glacialis* (g) populations in deeper waters and at surface.

Overall, *Calanus* had rather low lipid, even the overwintering stages. The young copepodite stages had a lipid sac to prosome area ratio of <0.2, with many individuals having no visible lipid sac at all. *Calanus* at depth had higher lipid content than those in surface waters (Figure 15, 16).

Figure 16: Lipid sac area to prosome area ratio (LAPA) of CIII, CIV and CV at depth and in surface waters at each station for entire *Calanus* population

Mesozooplankton community

In general, small copepods (*Pseudocalanus*, *Oithona similis*) as well as late larval stages of echinoderms, polychaets, and cirripedia dominated the surface samples in terms of abundance. South of the front, *Metridia longa* was very abundant in the deep samples, exceeding *Calanus* in numbers. The stations across the front also show a high abundance of Cladocera (*Evadne* sp).

References:

Macrozooplankton, pelagic fish, and acoustics

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Introduction

Oceanic fronts are defined by steep gradients in physical properties, but it is unresolved how tightly coupled these gradients are to the pelagic community structure across all size ranges and trophic levels. For many biota, the Barents Sea Polar Front represents thermal boundary between warm Atlantic and cold Arctic habitats¹⁻³ leading to variations in species composition, density, and functional traits (such as size and feeding mode) across the Polar Front. However, the Front does not constitute an absolute boundary as organisms are subjected to advection and mixing across frontal zones. Particularly on small scales, fronts and their biological manifestations can be highly dynamic and drifting organisms can be either concentrated or dispersed by the physical processes occurring at the Front. Higher densities of specific plankton size-fractions have been observed in frontal zones⁴⁻⁶ with enhanced eddy formation along frontal zones⁷ leading to patches of elevated plankton concentrations⁶. The Polar Front has been suggested to be an important feeding area for several fish species⁸. Which species aggregate, where and why they do so, and how this varies seasonally, however, is poorly understood. The main aim of the macrozooplankton, pelagic fish, and acoustics sampling is to define changes in terms of species composition, distribution, abundance and biomass across the front. We relate this variability to the physical properties of the frontal structure. We also document stomach contents and lipid concentrations in fish to assess how these intermediate trophic levels contribute to the flow of energy across ecosystem (e.g., wasp-waist control⁹). Finally, we will use the broadband acoustic-trawl datasets to classify the frequency-response curves (i.e., acoustic signature) of the dominant taxa.

Tucker Trawl

Macrozooplankton were sampled with a Tucker trawl (1 m² opening and 1000 µm mesh size; Figure 17) towed for 10 minutes at 2 knots. Each station was sampled a minimum of two times, with 4 stations sampled three times due to multiple acoustic scattering layers of interest. The targeted depth at each station was determined from the epipelagic SSL identified in the echogram from the vessel's echosounder. Relative abundance from the Tucker trawl samples were analysed per station. The length distribution of krill was measured from subsamples and each taxa were dried in pre-weighted recipients for dry weight measurements.

Figure 17: The tucker trawl (A) and sorting the catch (B-D), and the largest individual of *Cyanea capillata* caught in the trawl.

Harstad Pelagic Trawl

We deployed a Harstad pelagic trawl (Figure 18) within the sound scattering layer to ground-truth the acoustic signal and collect fish for stomach content, and stable isotope analysis. In six out of the nine sites two pelagic trawls were as fish distribution appeared stratified with a shallow sound scattering layer and a deep one. The Harstad trawl had an opening of 18.28 m x 18.28 m and an effective height of 9-11 m and width of 10-12 m at 3 knots. The mesh size of the inner liner of the cod end was 10 mm. The Harstad trawl was towed at ca. 3 knots for roughly 15 min. All organisms were identified to lowest taxonomic level possible onboard. We recorded the total number and weight of each species.

Figure 18: Fulmars enjoying the jellyfish (A), releasing the catch from the pelagic trawl (B), sorting and taking measurements of the trawl catch (C, D), species caught at PF4 (E), and age-0 capelin from PF9 (F).

Stomach Contents

Fish caught by the Harstad pelagic trawl will be used for diet and stable isotope analysis. For large catches, subsamples of 25-50 individuals from each abundantly caught fish were taken as a representation of the length distributions of the species. The standard length, height at the anus (up to the nearest 1mm), and weight (up to the nearest 0.1g) were measured for all specimens in the subsample. The fish were then dissected onboard to remove stomachs, preserving the remainder of the fish at -20°C for stable isotope analysis at a later point. The stomachs were immediately preserved in 70% ethanol, and further analysis on the contents will be conducted by trained and experienced personnel after the conclusion of the cruise. For each individual stomach, the level of fullness (from 0: empty, to 4: full), prey composition (the count and % volume each prey item takes up in the stomach), and the level of digestion for each prey item (from 1: newly eaten, to 5: digested or non-identifiable) will be estimated and recorded.

Hull-mounted EK60

The keel-mounted Simrad EK60® split-beam echosounder continuously recorded hydroacoustic data at 18, 38, and 120 kHz. The ping rate was set to 1.5 seconds and pulse length to 1,024 μ s. The echosounder was calibrated annually (Supplementary Table 1) using the standard sphere method¹⁰. A Seabird 911 Plus CTD® recorded temperature and conductivity regularly throughout the transects from which we could derive profiles of temperature and salinity, sound speed¹¹, and the coefficient of absorption at each frequency¹².

Table 9. Sampling operations conducted by the macrozooplankton, fish, and acoustics team

<i>Station</i>	<i>Event ID</i>	<i>Date (UTC)</i>	<i>Time (UTC)</i>	<i>Sampling Depth (m)</i>	<i>Sampling Time (min)</i>	<i>Tucker Trawl</i>	<i>Pelagic Trawl</i>
PF1	1086	17/08/23	17:57	100	11	x	
PF1	1087	17/08/23	18:37	300	10	x	
PF1	1088	17/08/23	19:13	180	10	x	
PF1	1098	17/08/23	01:00	300	14		x
PF2	1112	18/08/23	11:41	40	10	x	
PF2	1113	18/08/23	12:10	200	10	x	
PF2	1114	18/08/23	12:49	260	11	x	
PF2	1128	18/08/23	20:30	180	15		x
PF2	1129	18/08/23	21:24	230	18		x
PF3	1134	19/08/23	7:04	200	11	x	
PF3	1135	19/08/23	7:37	120	12	x	
PF3	1136	19/08/23	7:59	20	11	x	
PF3	1149	19/08/23	14:28:04	140	16		x
PF4	1154	20/08/23	6:58	150	11	x	
PF4	1155	20/08/23	7:29	25	11	x	
PF4	1169	20/08/23	13:54:00	40	13		x
PF4	1170	20/08/23	14:43:00	125	13		x
PF5	1174	21/08/23	7:04	140	11	x	
PF5	1175	21/08/23	7:42	90	11	x	
PF5	1176	21/08/23	8:07	25	12	x	
PF5	1187	21/08/23	13:49:00	40	16		x
PF5	1188	21/08/23	14:39	120	~15		x
PF6	1200	22/08/23	7:03	40	16	x	
PF6	1201	22/08/23	7:40	120	14	x	
PF6	1218	22/08/23	14:56	100	11		x
PF6	1219	22/08/23	15:41	40	15		x
PF7	1227	23/08/23	6:57	80	11	x	
PF7	1228	23/08/23	7:40	180	11	x	
PF7	1241	23/08/23	13:56	100	15		x
PF7	1242	23/08/23	14:46:00	180	15		x
PF8	1250	24/08/23	7:07	200	9	x	
PF8	1251	24/08/23	7:52	100	11	x	
PF8	1260	24/08/23	13:19	90	13		x
PF8	1261	24/08/23	14:04	200	14		x
PF9	1272	25/08/23	6:54	30	14	x	
PF9	1273	25/08/23	7:42	220	12	x	
PF9	1283	25/08/23	13:44	220	16		x

Preliminary results

Figure 19: Biomass of *Cyanea capillata* from the pelagic trawl per 15 minutes trawling at each station.

- 1) High number of *Cyanea capillata* were caught by all nets independent of depth. Wet weight of *C. capillata* caught by the Tucker trawl ranged from 0.044 - 6.9 kg, and from the pelagic trawl ranged from 2.0-42.86 kg. The largest specimen caught measured 49 cm across the bell and weighed 6.9kg (Figure 19).

Figure 20: Relative species count composition from the Tucker trawl per station.

- 2) High jellyfish (hydrozoans) diversity was caught by the tucker trawl. 14 different species were identified onboard. Jellyfish diversity appeared to increase with proximity to the front. The highest diversity, standardized by number of tows, was caught at station PF6.

- 3) Tucker trawl krill (*Thysanoessa longicaudata*, *Thysanoessa inermis*, and *Meganyctiphanes norvegica*, in relative order of abundance) biomass caught decrease with increasing latitude. Krill were caught in higher abundance south of the front, and in deeper water compared to shallower (Figure 20)
- 4) *Thysanoessa longicaudata* was the most commonly caught krill species in both trawls.

Figure 21: relative fish species weight composition from the pelagic trawl per station.

- 5) Fish biomass caught by the Harstad trawl ranged from 0.39 – 23.5kg. The predominant fish species caught at all stations was Capelin (*Mallotus villosus*). Size of Capelin ranged from 3.2 – 15.1cm, with larger individuals caught further north (Figure 21).
- 6) A large number of age-0 Polar cod (*Boreogadus saida*) was caught in the northern five stations. We estimate that approximately 7184 individuals were caught in total.
- 7) Most fish caught appeared to be eating and had some prey in their stomachs. From a few samples analyzed on board fish appeared to be eating small krill, copepods, amphipods and cladocerans.
- 8) Acoustic backscatter from 16/08/23-19/08/23, the first front crossing, suggests a change in fish and macrozooplankton distribution north and south of the Front. South of the Polar Front we observed what appears to be backscatter from dispersed organisms with more dense aggregations at deeper depths (Figure 22). North of the front acoustic backscatter is concentrated in deep waters without much in the top and middle of the water column.

Figure 22. EK60 echograms from 16/08/23-19/08/23, the first crossing of the Polar Front.

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Glider data sampling for Polar Front mission summer 2023

Håvard Buschmann, ApN

A fleet of gliders was deployed during the cruise to extend the spatial and temporal resolution of the data collection. The Seagliders (Hydroid M1), collected data for hydrography, zooplankton images and broadband hydroacoustic throughout the water column. An autonomous surface vehicle, Sailbuoys (Offshore Sensing Ltd.), equipped with acoustic instruments collected data on water velocity and biological backscatter as well as surface hydrography data across the polar front. An Otter (Marine Robotics) was deployed on short term deployments to collect acoustic data in the vicinity of Helmer Hanssen.

Table 10: Deployment and recovery date/time

Glider	Deployment	Recovery
SB echo 1 (EK80)	18. august 2023	TBD
Seaglider SG 644	18. august 2023	25. august 2023
Otto-Otter (Otter USV)	Deployed and retrieved 18., 22. & 23. August 2023	N/A

Sensor data volume (in nr or recordings or freq and duration)

SB echo 1 (EK80)

Sensor	Parameters	Sampling freq./duty cycle	Nr data points recorded or similar
Datalogger (D)	CT, EchoTriplet (Fluo), O2	Every 30 min	TBA
EK80 (200kHz transducer)	backscatter	On 15 min every 30 min (50% of the time)	TBA

SG 644 (CSCS)

Sensor	Parameter	Sampling freq./duty cycle	Nr data points recorded or similar
CT	CT	Every 5 secs	TBA
Optode	O2	Every 5 secs	TBA
GPS	Lat/long	Every surfacing	TBA
EK80 (333 kHz) single beam	Acoustic backscatter	Continuous during descent	TBA
UVP6	images	2Hz at 0-100m depth, 0.5 Hz below 100 m, based on glider pressure	TBA
SeaOwl	Chla, FDOM, backscatter	Every 10 secs	TBA
Depth	depth	Dive to seafloor	TBA

Otto-Otter (Otter USV)

Sensor	Parameter	Sampling freq./duty cycle	Nr data points recorded or similar
EK80 (333 kHz split broadband, 200kHz single CW, 38kHz split CW)	Acoustic backscatter	Continuous	22GB from 3 deployments
Winch with CTD (AML3) down to 100m	CTD & Fluorescein	2Hz (when commanded)	8 profiles to 100m
Seapath positioning system	Lat/long, heading, pitch, roll, heave	Continuous	Stored in EK80 data

Issues during deployment (malfunctionings and problems)

Sailbuoy

SB Echo 1 was set out the 18th and started logging (CT, eco triplet and optode) every 5 minutes, with echosounder at a 1-minute interval every 15 minutes. This was changed to 15 minutes every 30 minutes the 21. At 14:00. And logging every 30 minutes. This was done to preserve power and provide more continuous echosounder data.

Voltage has been at a stable 13.1V since the change. Should this however drop below 12V, the cycle for echosounder could be reduced to 20 minutes every 2nd 30-minute cycle (33% of the time), to preserve power.

Seaglider

The glider was deployed the 18th but showed early signs of steering difficulty. Based off a picture from deployment CSCS (Cyprus Subsea Consulting & Services) figured the lack of steerability was due to the UVP6 sensor being mounted incorrectly. The 21st of August, after the last trawl was finished, the ship travelled north to the glider, and it was recovered. The UVP6 sensor was then correctly mounted according to CSCS. It was redeployed after a short travel southward. It did however still possess the earlier symptoms, and after numerous compass calibrations CSCS concluded that the compass was at fault.

Figure 23: The Seaglider with the UVP6 sensor in the nose, rotated to its correct position

Otter

The Otter was first deployed the 18th of august, and this served as a test of the echosounders, CTD and Starlink. The 333kHz transducer provided so much noise, the data is believed to be unusable. However, the 38kHz and 200kHz seemed good. Numerous configurations were tested on the echosounders, and it was decided to not use the 333kHz. It's also worthy to note that a lot of equipment on the cruise uses echosounders, which in some cases provided interference.

This was also the first time the AML3 CTD was used since it's calibration, repair and firmware upgrade. The CTD has an automatic water detection start, which means it starts logging once it detects water, a programmed value for its sensor's parameters. Due to waves and frequent pitching of the Otter the CTD was partly getting splashes of water causing it to continually log until the battery ran empty. On the 18th and 22nd, only one cast was logged. After the deployment on the 18th the water detection parameter for pressure was changed, however data from the 22nd showed that it also starts on parameters for conductivity. This was also changed and the deployment on the 23rd provided clean CTD casts.

On the 22nd the Seapath navigation system was unable to acquire heading. This led to the echosounder data being without positioning. In order to use this data, we then must use the FF *Helmer Hanssen*'s AIS position as reference. The issue was fixed the corresponding day by correcting the GPS antennas on the Otter (vibration may have misaligned them), as well as different software tweaks.

The 18th was also the first proper test of the Starlink system. However, the 4G modem inside the Otter caused some internet traffic to divert to it, leading nowhere. The 4G modem was then removed, which proved successful for the deployments on the 22nd and 23rd of august.

The Otter is equipped with two 915Wh batteries. On the 23rd the VCS (Vehicle Control Station) reported a missing battery about halfway through the deployment. It was at first believed to be just a software bug; however, the rapid battery consumption and lack of motor power is evidence of the battery not correctly working. On the 24th one of the magnetic switches was unable to turn the batteries on. These switches also monitor the battery. Maritime Robotics, the Otter's producer believe the switch to be faulty and in need of a replacement. They also advised not to run the Otter on a single battery since it's not able to provide sufficient energy for the electric motors. Which meant the Otter could not participate further in the cruise.

Figure 24: The FF Helmer Hanssen from the camera of Otto-Otter

Data acquisition and piloting

Sailbuoy

At 8:20 the Sailbuoy was manually set to a steering tack to go with the wind for deployment. It was deployed at 77.76327N 29.45253E (decimal degrees) around 9:30 UTC by attaching a quick-release hook on the back brace and released once floating in the water. At 10:50 the Sailbuoy was set to automatically steer south, and datalogger was turned on (sampling every 5 minutes, and echosounder for 1 minute every 15 minutes). At 18:50 a stricter passage for the autopilot was set to get it closer to 29.5 degrees east. At 8:00 the 20th of august the sailbuoy had reached 77.0 degrees north alongside 29.5 degrees east and was instructed to go north again.

At 15:25 the 21st the datalogger settings were changed for more infrequent data sampling, but more continuous echosounder data. (Sampling every 30 minutes, and echosounder for 15 minutes every 30 minutes).

At 9:00 the 25th the Sailbuoy was instructed to automatically go between 77.6 degrees north to 77.0 degrees north alongside 29.5 east and turn around once waypoint was reached. At 17:15 the 25th the sailbuoy reached the waypoint at 77.6 degrees north and turned south again.

The sailbuoy has no planned retrieval and will sail down to the 12mile zone outside Tromsø for pickup after the cruise has ended. High resolution data from the datalogger and WBT (echosounder) will be acquired once the Sailbuoy has been recovered to Akvaplan-niva in Tromsø.

Figure 25: Track showing the Sailbuoy's movement from the 18th to the 26th of August.

Seaglider

The SG644 Seaglider is piloted and controlled by CSCS in Cyprus. It was deployed the 18th around 9:30 at 77.76 degrees by crane, quick-release hook and a steering rope. Once the glider was sufficiently in the water the release hook was pulled and the steering rope thrown to the Polarcirkel MOB (Man overboard boat). With the strap and steering rope still attached, a buoyancy test was done by “drowning” the glider. Once the glider was deemed seaworthy the strap was removed and a dive signal was sent to CSCS in Cyprus. FF Helmer Hansen waited for the first short dive to make sure the glider functioned as expected and an ok was given from CSCS.

The gliders plan was to head south along 29.5 degrees to cross the polar front. Issues previously mentioned resulted in a recovery and redeployment. The redeployment was also further south at 77.5 degrees north to hopefully allow it to pass the polar front. According to CSCS the sensors supposedly works fine and is acquiring data. The glider mostly carried on east after redeployment. It was recovered on Friday the 25th by use of MOB. High resolution data from the UVP6, WBT (echosounder) and datalogger will be acquisitioned upon retrieval of the glider in Cyprus.

Figure 26: Track showing the Seaglidiers movement

Otter

The Otter was first deployed the 18th by crane and a quick-release hook. Battery life was expected to be around 5-6 hours, but due to Starlink this was shortened to 4-5hours. The Otter was supposed to do transects to and from the boat and doing CTD casts, which was accomplished by doing transects with and from the ships drift. The ships drift meant that one of the transects were shorter. Waves at the end of the deployment the 18th proved too difficult for the otter the properly navigate. However, the deployment was mainly used to test and verify different settings. There was also some usable data gathered. The echosounder was on where possible and turned on passive when Frankenstein (Einats EK80) was on. One CTD cast was properly recorded and 10GB of echosounder data gathered. Recovery was done by “Otter fishing”, using the crane’s hook and fish for the Otters brace.

On the 22nd the Otter was again deployed by the same method. A lot of time on this deployment was used for troubleshooting. It was eventually decided to just start the echosounders. The deployment served successful for the Starlink, with Pierre Priou controlling and monitoring the echosounders from Tromsø. One CTD cast was properly recorded and 7,3GB of echosounder data gathered. Retrieval was then done by use of a MOB and crew attaching the cranes hook directly to the Otters brace.

On the 23rd the Otter was again deployed by the same method. All systems were normal, and the Otter made transects to and from the boat, casting the CTD at each turn. The deployment was run short due to a battery issue, about halfway through. 6 CTD casts were recorded and 5GB of echosounder data gathered. The Otter was again recovered using a MOB.

Figure 27: Otter being recovered by crane.

Outreach

<https://akvaplan.no/no/nyhet/2023-08-23/gjennombrudd-i-bruk-av-autonom-teknologi-i-studie-av-polarfronten>

Appendix I - Sample log

Event #	Station	Latitude °N	Longitude °E	Bottom depth (m)	Sampling date (UTC)	Sampling time UTC (start)	Gear	Sampling depth (m) from	Sampling depth (m) to	Sample type	Sample staff	Preservation method
1085	PF1	75.00	29.50	370	16.08.2023	17:23:50	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1085	PF1	75.00	29.50	370	16.08.2023	17:23:50	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1085	PF1	75.00	29.50	370	16.08.2023	17:23:50	CTD with water	360		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1086	PF1	75.00	29.50	369	16.08.2023	17:50:52	Tucker trawl	100		community, biomass	Einat	not kept
1087	PF1	75.00	29.46	370	16.08.2023	18:19:39	Tucker trawl	300		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1088	PF1	75.00	29.40	365	16.08.2023	19:02:59	Tucker trawl	180		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1089	PF1	75.00	29.37	368	16.08.2023	19:39:44	Phytoplankton net	30	0	community	Eva	
1090	PF1	75.00	29.38	367	16.08.2023	19:58:53	FFFR	100	0		Rolf	
1091	PF1	75.00	29.40	366	16.08.2023	20:16:52	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1091	PF1	75.00	29.40	366	16.08.2023	20:16:52	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1091	PF1	75.00	29.40	366	16.08.2023	20:16:52	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1092	PF1	75.00	29.42	367	16.08.2023	20:42:59	Multinet 180μ	345	200	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1092	PF1	75.00	29.42	367	16.08.2023	20:42:59	Multinet 180μ	200	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1092	PF1	75.00	29.42	367	16.08.2023	20:42:59	Multinet 180μ	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1092	PF1	75.00	29.42	367	16.08.2023	20:42:59	Multinet 180μ	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1092	PF1	75.00	29.42	367	16.08.2023	20:42:59	Multinet 180μ	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1093	PF1	74.99	29.45	371	16.08.2023	21:32:21	WP2 180μ	365	0	biomass	Malin	Dry weight
1094	PF1	74.99	29.47	371	16.08.2023	22:05:49	WP2 180μ	360	200	lipid images	Malin	ethanol
1095	PF1	74.99	29.49	371	16.08.2023	22:35:20	WP2 180μ	50	0	lipid images	Malin	ethanol
1096	PF1	74.99	29.50	372	16.08.2023	22:47:38	WP3	100	0	egg production	Malin	not kept
1097	PF1	74.99	29.53	374	16.08.2023	23:31:48	Frankenstein	360	0		Sunnje	
1098	PF1	75.00	29.52	373	17.08.2023	00:45:40	Pelagic trawl	300		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1099	PF1	74.99	29.50	371	17.08.2023	02:13:14	MVP				Sunnje	
1100		76.11	29.50	301	17.08.2023	12:36:32	CTD				Sunnje	
1101		76.11	29.52	299	17.08.2023	12:51:28	MVP				Sunnje	
1102		76.10	29.50	301	17.08.2023	13:36:38	MVP				Sunnje	
1103		76.61	29.50	252	17.08.2023	18:22:03	CTD				Sunnje	
1104		76.61	29.50	254	17.08.2023	18:34:27	FRRF	100	0		Rolf	
1105		76.61	29.50	253	17.08.2023	19:24:45	MVP				Sunnje	
1106		77.77	29.50	230	18.08.2023	06:17:59	CTD					
1107		77.77	29.49	228	18.08.2023	06:39:55	FRRF				Rolf	
1108		77.77	29.48	227	18.08.2023	07:41:39	Glider deployment				Håvard	

1109		77.76	29.48	225	18.08.2023	07:56:24	Sail buoy deployment				Håvard	
1110		77.76	29.50	230	18.08.2023	08:53:34	MVP				Sünnje	
1111	PF2	78.01	29.50	324	18.08.2023	11:15:52	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1111	PF2	78.01	29.50	324	18.08.2023	11:15:52	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1111	PF2	78.01	29.50	324	18.08.2023	11:15:52	CTD with water	315		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1112	PF2	78.01	29.48	330	18.08.2023	11:36:15	Tucker trawl	40		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1113	PF2	78.00	29.35	328	18.08.2023	12:37:57	Tucker trawl	200		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1114	PF2	78.00	29.35	329	18.08.2023	12:38:19	Tucker trawl	260		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1115	PF2	78.00	29.27	328	18.08.2023	13:21:16	Otto Otter deployment				Håvard	
1116	PF2	78.00	29.25	331	18.08.2023	13:30:32	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1117	PF2	78.00	29.25	330	18.08.2023	13:44:28	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1118	PF2	78.00	29.25	331	18.08.2023	13:56:52	FRRF				Rolf	
1119	PF2	78.00	29.26	331	18.08.2023	14:10:44	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1119	PF2	78.00	29.26	331	18.08.2023	14:10:44	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1119	PF2	78.00	29.26	331	18.08.2023	14:10:44	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1120	PF2	78.00	29.27	328	18.08.2023	14:32:58	EK80				Einat	
1121	PF2	78.00	29.31	326	18.08.2023	15:46:11	Multinet	310	200	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1121	PF2	78.00	29.31	326	18.08.2023	15:46:11	Multinet	200	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1121	PF2	78.00	29.31	326	18.08.2023	15:46:11	Multinet	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1121	PF2	78.00	29.31	326	18.08.2023	15:46:11	Multinet	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1121	PF2	78.00	29.31	326	18.08.2023	15:46:11	Multinet	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1122	PF2	77.99	29.36	330	18.08.2023	16:40:52	WP3	315	0	egg incubation	Malin	not kept
1123	PF2	77.99	29.36	328	18.08.2023	17:00:39	WP2 180µ	315	0	biomass	Malin	dryweight
1124	PF2	77.98	29.37	330	18.08.2023	17:31:20	WP2 180µ	315	200	lipid images, females for egg inc.	Malin	ethanol
1125	PF2	77.98	29.37	330	18.08.2023	17:47:12	WP2 180µ	50	0	lipid images	Malin	not kept
1126	PF2	77.98	29.37	329	18.08.2023	17:52:41	WP2 180µ	100	0	egg incubation	Malin	not kept
1127	PF2	77.97	29.37	327	18.08.2023	18:12:08	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1128	PF2	77.99	29.42	332	18.08.2023	20:29:55	Pelagic trawl	180		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1129	PF2	78.03	29.50	332	18.08.2023	21:24:25	Pelagic trawl	230		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1130	PFx	78.50	29.50	233	19.08.2023	00:44:36	CTD					
1131	PFx	78.50	29.50	233	19.08.2023	00:56:57	FRRF				Rolf	
1132	PFx	78.50	29.49	234	19.08.2023	01:11:50	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1133	PF3	77.74	29.49	231	19.08.2023	06:28:05	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1133	PF3	77.74	29.49	231	19.08.2023	06:28:05	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1133	PF3	77.74	29.49	231	19.08.2023	06:28:05	CTD with water	220		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1134	PF3	77.74	29.49	233	19.08.2023	06:50:46	Tucker trawl	200		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1135	PF3	77.72	29.43	227	19.08.2023	07:28:44	Tucker trawl	125		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight

1136	PF3	77.71	29.39	222	19.08.2023	07:58:06	Tucker trawl	25		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1137	PF3	77.75	29.50	227	19.08.2023	08:40:12	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1138	PF3	77.75	29.49	228	19.08.2023	08:50:06	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1139	PF3	77.75	29.49	228	19.08.2023	09:03:10	FRRF				Rolf	
1140	PF3	77.74	29.49	229	19.08.2023	09:14:09	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1140	PF3	77.74	29.49	229	19.08.2023	09:14:09	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1140	PF3	77.74	29.49	229	19.08.2023	09:14:09	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1141	PF3	77.74	29.49	233	19.08.2023	09:34:12	EK80				Einat	
1142	PF3	77.73	29.49	229	19.08.2023	10:28:32	EK80				Einat	
1143	PF3	77.72	29.51	223	19.08.2023	11:15:59	Multinet	205	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1143	PF3	77.72	29.51	223	19.08.2023	11:15:59	Multinet	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1143	PF3	77.72	29.51	223	19.08.2023	11:15:59	Multinet	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1143	PF3	77.72	29.51	223	19.08.2023	11:15:59	Multinet	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1144	PF3	77.70	29.51	204	19.08.2023	12:13:15	WP2 180µ	195	0	biomass	Malin	Dry weight
1145	PF3	77.70	29.51	207	19.08.2023	12:33:17	WP2 180µ	191	0	community	Malin	ethanol
1146	PF3	77.70	29.50	207	19.08.2023	12:58:44	WP2 180µ	195	150	lipid images	Malin	not kept
1147	PF3	77.70	29.49	205	19.08.2023	13:07:05	WP2 180µ	50	0	lipid images	Malin	not kept
1148	PF3	77.70	29.49	209	19.08.2023	13:26:20	Frankenstein				Sunnje	
1149	PF3	77.73	29.48	229	19.08.2023	14:27:01	Pelagic trawl	130			Frida	
1150	PF3.5	77.63	29.50	195	19.08.2023	18:28:15	CTD					
1151	PF3.5	77.63	29.49	200	19.08.2023	18:42:56	FRRF				Rolf	
1152	PF3.5	77.63	29.49	199	19.08.2023	18:55:30	Frankenstein				Sunnje	
1153	PF4	77.50	29.44	190	20.08.2023	06:27:07	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1153	PF4	77.50	29.44	190	20.08.2023	06:27:07	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1153	PF4	77.50	29.44	190	20.08.2023	06:27:07	CTD with water	220		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1154	PF4	77.50	29.43	191	20.08.2023	06:44:25	Tucker trawl	140		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1155	PF4	77.52	29.36	183	20.08.2023	07:25:30	Tucker trawl	25		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1156	PF4	77.51	29.48	198	20.08.2023	08:07:44	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1157	PF4	77.51	29.48	201	20.08.2023	08:12:42	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1158	PF4	77.51	29.48	202	20.08.2023	08:20:18	FRRF				Rolf	
1159	PF4	77.51	29.47	199	20.08.2023	08:30:20	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1159	PF4	77.51	29.47	199	20.08.2023	08:30:20	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1159	PF4	77.51	29.47	199	20.08.2023	08:30:20	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1160	PF4	77.51	29.47	199	20.08.2023	08:46:44	EK80				Einat	
1161	PF4	77.51	29.45	192	20.08.2023	09:45:02	EK80				Einat	
1162	PF4	77.52	29.42	189	20.08.2023	10:39:03	Multinet	175	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1162	PF4	77.52	29.42	189	20.08.2023	10:39:03	Multinet	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1162	PF4	77.52	29.42	189	20.08.2023	10:39:03	Multinet	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin

1162	PF4	77.52	29.42	189	20.08.2023	10:39:03	Multinet	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1163	PF4	77.51	29.39	189	20.08.2023	11:19:41	WP2 180µ	175	0	biomass	Malin	Dry weight
1164	PF4	77.51	29.37	185	20.08.2023	11:46:39	WP2 180µ	175	100	community	Malin	not kept
1165	PF4	77.50	29.36	184	20.08.2023	12:22:13	WP2 180µ	175	100	images	Malin	ethanol
1166	PF4	77.50	29.35	183	20.08.2023	12:33:20	WP2 180µ	50	20	community	Malin	4% formalin
1167	PF4	77.50	29.35	182	20.08.2023	12:46:15	WP2 180µ	50	0	images	Malin	ethanol
1168	PF4	77.50	29.35	182	20.08.2023	12:57:38	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1169	PF4	77.51	29.37	186	20.08.2023	13:53:13	Pelagic trawl	40		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1170	PF4	77.54	29.42	196	20.08.2023	14:29:29	Pelagic trawl	125		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1171		77.43	29.49	186	20.08.2023	16:10:32	CTD					
1172		77.43	29.49	183	20.08.2023	16:20:16	FRRF				Rolf	
1173	PF5	77.38	29.48	185	21.08.2023	06:29:33	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1173	PF5	77.38	29.48	185	21.08.2023	06:29:33	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1173	PF5	77.38	29.48	185	21.08.2023	06:29:33	CTD with water	180		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1174	PF5	77.38	29.46	183	21.08.2023	06:48:47	Tucker trawl	140		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1175	PF5	77.39	29.38	178	21.08.2023	07:31:16	Tucker trawl	90		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1176	PF5	77.39	29.32	179	21.08.2023	08:03:41	Tucker trawl	25		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1177	PF5	77.38	29.50	181	21.08.2023	08:48:27	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1178	PF5	77.37	29.48	179	21.08.2023	09:02:52	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1179	PF5	77.37	29.47	179	21.08.2023	09:09:48	FRRF				Rolf	
1180	PF5	77.37	29.46	180	21.08.2023	09:19:22	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1180	PF5	77.37	29.46	180	21.08.2023	09:19:22	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1180	PF5	77.37	29.46	180	21.08.2023	09:19:22	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1181	PF5	77.37	29.44	182	21.08.2023	09:39:15	EK80				Einat	
1182	PF5	77.36	29.36	182	21.08.2023	10:59:47	Multinet	168	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1182	PF5	77.36	29.36	182	21.08.2023	10:59:47	Multinet	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1182	PF5	77.36	29.36	182	21.08.2023	10:59:47	Multinet	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1182	PF5	77.36	29.36	182	21.08.2023	10:59:47	Multinet	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1183	PF5	77.37	29.48	182	21.08.2023	12:09:45	WP2 180µ				Malin	failed
1183	PF5	77.37	29.47	178	21.08.2023	12:22:48	WP2 180µ	175	0	biomass	Malin	Dry weight
1184	PF5	77.37	29.47	179	21.08.2023	12:24:02	WP2 180µ	175	100	images	Malin	not kept
1185	PF5	77.37	29.46	180	21.08.2023	12:38:01	WP2 180µ	50	0	images	Malin	not kept
1186	PF5	77.37	29.45	183	21.08.2023	12:55:31	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1187	PF5	77.38	29.48	183	21.08.2023	13:47:19	Pelagic trawl	40		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1188	PF5	77.40	29.59	189	21.08.2023	14:26:37	Pelagic trawl	120		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1189	PF3b	77.70	29.45	210	21.08.2023	16:54:08	Glider pick up				Håvard	
1190	PF3b	77.75	29.47	231	21.08.2023	18:03:49	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1191	PF3.5b	77.63	29.49	198	21.08.2023	19:25:50	Frankenstein				Sünnje	

1192		77.50	29.48	197	21.08.2023	20:52:11	GLIDER				Håvard	
1193	PF4.5b	77.44	29.49	187	21.08.2023	22:00:29	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1194	PF5b	77.37	29.47	181	22.08.2023	22:58:23	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1195		77.32	29.50	182	22.08.2023	00:36:22	CTD					
1196		77.32	29.50	182	22.08.2023	00:46:09	FRRF				Rolf	
1197	PF5.5	77.31	29.49	182	22.08.2023	00:56:01	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1198	PF6	77.25	29.50	192	22.08.2023	06:28:56	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1198	PF6	77.25	29.50	192	22.08.2023	06:28:56	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1199	PF6	77.25	29.49	194	22.08.2023	06:44:22	CTD with water	180		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1200	PF6	77.25	29.48	193	22.08.2023	06:58:08	Tucker trawl	40		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1201	PF6	77.26	29.43	188	22.08.2023	07:26:42	Tucker trawl	120		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1202	PF6	77.25	29.50	193	22.08.2023	08:36:59	GLIDER				Håvard	
1203	PF6	77.25	29.49	192	22.08.2023	08:42:58	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1204	PF6	77.25	29.49	193	22.08.2023	08:50:12	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1205	PF6	77.25	29.48	193	22.08.2023	08:58:19	FRRF				Rolf	
1206	PF6	77.25	29.47	193	22.08.2023	09:08:38	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1206	PF6	77.25	29.47	193	22.08.2023	09:08:38	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1206	PF6	77.25	29.47	193	22.08.2023	09:08:38	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1207	PF6	77.24	29.45	194	22.08.2023	09:37:12	EK80				Einat	
1208	PF6	77.23	29.40	191	22.08.2023	11:00:13	Multinet	170	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1208	PF6	77.23	29.40	191	22.08.2023	11:00:13	Multinet	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1208	PF6	77.23	29.40	191	22.08.2023	11:00:13	Multinet	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1208	PF6	77.23	29.40	191	22.08.2023	11:00:13	Multinet	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1209	PF6	77.23	29.37	193	22.08.2023	11:38:24	WP2 180µ				Malin	
1210	PF6	77.23	29.35	194	22.08.2023	12:08:09	WP2 180µ				Malin	
1211	PF6	77.22	29.35	197	22.08.2023	12:24:25	WP2 180µ				Malin	
1212	PF6	77.22	29.34	195	22.08.2023	12:41:35	WP2 180µ	185	0	biomass	Malin	Dry weight
1213	PF6	77.22	29.33	197	22.08.2023	12:56:43	WP2 180µ	190	100	images	Malin	not kept
1214	PF6	77.22	29.32	197	22.08.2023	13:12:35	WP2 180µ	50	0	images	Malin	not kept
1215	PF6	77.22	29.31	199	22.08.2023	13:31:03	WP2 180µ				Malin	
1216	PF6	77.22	29.31	199	22.08.2023	13:43:23	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1217	PF6	77.22	29.29	199	22.08.2023	14:20:23	Otter pick up				Håvard	Håvard
1218	PF6	77.23	29.34	194	22.08.2023	14:51:44	Pelagic trawl	100		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1219	PF6	77.25	29.47	191	22.08.2023	15:39:38	Pelagic trawl	40		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1220	PF6.3	77.17	29.50	203	22.08.2023	16:53:03	CTD					
1221	PF6.3	77.17	29.49	203	22.08.2023	17:09:34	FRRF				Rolf	
1222	PF6.3	77.17	29.49	204	22.08.2023	17:19:31	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1223	PF6.6	77.09	29.50	211	22.08.2023	18:23:18	CTD					

1224	PF6.6	77.09	29.49	209	22.08.2023	18:34:55	FRRF				Rolf	
1225	PF6.6	77.09	29.49	210	22.08.2023	18:46:53	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1226	PF7	77.01	29.52	227	23.08.2023	06:28:51	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1226	PF7	77.01	29.52	227	23.08.2023	06:28:51	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1226	PF7	77.01	29.52	227	23.08.2023	06:28:51	CTD with water	220		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1227	PF7	77.01	29.51	229	23.08.2023	06:46:15	Tucker trawl	80		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1228	PF7	77.02	29.48	226	23.08.2023	07:18:45	Tucker trawl	180		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1229	PF7	77.00	29.50	228	23.08.2023	08:29:04	Otter deployed				Håvard	
1230	PF7	77.00	29.50	229	23.08.2023	08:37:57	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1231	PF7	77.00	29.50	232	23.08.2023	08:46:46	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1232	PF7	77.00	29.50	235	23.08.2023	08:54:14	FRRF				Rolf	
1233	PF7	77.00	29.50	234	23.08.2023	09:05:38	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1233	PF7	77.00	29.50	234	23.08.2023	09:05:38	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1233	PF7	77.00	29.50	234	23.08.2023	09:05:38	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1234	PF7	76.99	29.49	232	23.08.2023	09:24:17	EK80				Einat	
1235	PF7	76.99	29.48	236	23.08.2023	10:21:59	Multinet	220	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1235	PF7	76.99	29.48	236	23.08.2023	10:21:59	Multinet	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1235	PF7	76.99	29.48	236	23.08.2023	10:21:59	Multinet	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1235	PF7	76.99	29.48	236	23.08.2023	10:21:59	Multinet	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1236	PF7	76.98	29.47	234	23.08.2023	11:09:50	WP2 180µ	225	0	biomass	Malin	Dry weight
1237	PF7	76.98	29.45	237	23.08.2023	11:46:32	WP2 180µ	225	100	images	Malin	not kept
1238	PF7	76.98	29.45	237	23.08.2023	12:02:34	WP2 180µ	50	0	images	Malin	not kept
1239	PF7	76.97	29.45	236	23.08.2023	12:21:49	Otter retrieval				Håvard	
1240	PF7	77.00	29.50	234	23.08.2023	12:56:30	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1241	PF7	77.01	29.52	234	23.08.2023	13:48:35	Pelagic trawl	100		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1242	PF7	77.03	29.65	226	23.08.2023	14:35:00	Pelagic trawl	180		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1243	PF7.3	76.92	29.50	248	23.08.2023	16:19:36	CTD					
1244	PF7.3	76.92	29.50	249	23.08.2023	16:32:00	FRRF				Rolf	
1245	PF7.3	76.92	29.50	250	23.08.2023	16:41:34	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1246	PF7.6	76.84	29.50	251	23.08.2023	18:02:37	CTD					
1247	PF7.6	76.83	29.52	251	23.08.2023	19:26:04	FRRF				Rolf	
1248	PF7.6	76.83	29.52	249	23.08.2023	19:37:37	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1249	PF8	76.75	29.51	254	24.08.2023	06:28:45	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1249	PF8	76.75	29.51	254	24.08.2023	06:28:45	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1249	PF8	76.75	29.51	254	24.08.2023	06:28:45	CTD with water	245		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1250	PF8	76.75	29.52	254	24.08.2023	06:45:58	Tucker trawl	200		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1251	PF8	76.73	29.53	249	24.08.2023	07:39:57	Tucker trawl	100		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1252	PF8	76.75	29.51	252	24.08.2023	09:04:44	Phytoplankton net				Eva	

1253	PF8	76.75	29.51	251	24.08.2023	09:12:46	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1254	PF8	76.75	29.52	254	24.08.2023	09:23:14	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1254	PF8	76.75	29.52	254	24.08.2023	09:23:14	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1254	PF8	76.75	29.52	254	24.08.2023	09:23:14	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1255	PF8	76.75	29.52	254	24.08.2023	09:45:35	EK80				Einat	
1256	PF8	76.74	29.52	254	24.08.2023	10:22:27	Multinet	235	200	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1256	PF8	76.74	29.52	254	24.08.2023	10:22:27	Multinet	200	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1256	PF8	76.74	29.52	254	24.08.2023	10:22:27	Multinet	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1256	PF8	76.74	29.52	254	24.08.2023	10:22:27	Multinet	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1256	PF8	76.74	29.52	254	24.08.2023	10:22:27	Multinet	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1257	PF8	76.74	29.52	254	24.08.2023	11:14:17	WP2 180µ	245	0	biomass	Malin	Dry weight
1257	PF8	76.74	29.52	254	24.08.2023	11:14:17	WP2 180µ	245	200	images	Malin	not kept
1258	PF8	76.74	29.52	256	24.08.2023	11:41:03	WP2 180µ	50	0	images	Malin	not kept
1259	PF8	76.73	29.52	254	24.08.2023	12:15:57	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1260	PF8	76.74	29.51	255	24.08.2023	13:09:45	Pelagic trawl	100		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1261	PF8	76.78	29.51	259	24.08.2023	13:52:20	Pelagic trawl	200		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1262	PF8.25	76.64	29.50	262	24.08.2023	15:41:06	CTD					
1263	PF8.25	76.64	29.49	262	24.08.2023	15:54:28	FRRF				Rolf	
1264	PF8.25	76.64	29.49	261	24.08.2023	16:08:46	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1265	PF8.5	76.53	29.51	264	24.08.2023	17:39:35	FRRF				Rolf	
1266	PF8.5	76.53	29.52	266	24.08.2023	17:49:58	CTD					
1267	PF8.5	76.53	29.53	267	24.08.2023	18:01:45	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1268	PF8.75	76.43	29.50	268	24.08.2023	19:24:18	CTD					
1269	PF8.75	76.43	29.51	268	24.08.2023	19:37:42	FRRF				Rolf	
1270	PF8.75	76.43	29.51	268	24.08.2023	19:47:08	Frankenstein				Sünnje	
1271	PF9	76.32	29.49	274	25.08.2023	06:28:57	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1271	PF9	76.32	29.49	274	25.08.2023	06:28:57	CTD with water	20		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1271	PF9	76.32	29.49	274	25.08.2023	06:28:57	CTD with water	270		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1272	PF9	76.32	29.50	276	25.08.2023	06:47:55	Tucker trawl	35		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1273	PF9	76.31	29.48	278	25.08.2023	07:16:54	Tucker trawl	220		community, biomass	Einat	Dry weight
1274	PF9	76.32	29.49	277	25.08.2023	08:47:50	Phytoplankton net				Eva	
1275	PF9	76.32	29.50	277	25.08.2023	08:59:04	FRRF				Rolf	
1276	PF9	76.32	29.51	278	25.08.2023	09:08:19	CTD with water	5		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1276	PF9	76.32	29.51	278	25.08.2023	09:08:19	CTD with water	10		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1276	PF9	76.32	29.51	278	25.08.2023	09:08:19	CTD with water	100		Chla, Nutrients, POC/N, etc.	Eva	
1277	PF9	76.32	29.53	278	25.08.2023	09:32:07	EK80				Einat	
1278	PF9	76.32	29.58	275	25.08.2023	10:46:37	Multinet	260	200	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1278	PF9	76.32	29.58	275	25.08.2023	10:46:37	Multinet	200	100	community	Malin	4% Formalin

1278	PF9	76.32	29.58	275	25.08.2023	10:46:37	Multinet	100	50	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1278	PF9	76.32	29.58	275	25.08.2023	10:46:37	Multinet	50	20	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1278	PF9	76.32	29.58	275	25.08.2023	10:46:37	Multinet	20	0	community	Malin	4% Formalin
1279	PF9	76.31	29.61	274	25.08.2023	11:34:25	WP2 180µ	265	0	biomass	Malin	Dry weight
1280	PF9	76.31	29.63	276	25.08.2023	12:02:56	WP2 180µ	265	200	images	Malin	not kept
1281	PF9	76.31	29.64	277	25.08.2023	12:20:48	WP2 180µ	50	0	images	Malin	not kept
1282	PF9	76.32	29.64	277	25.08.2023	12:33:30	Frankenstein					
1283	PF9	76.31	29.60	275	25.08.2023	13:33:47	Pelagic trawl	220		biomass, stomach content	Frida	
1284		77.50	29.51	191	25.08.2023	22:30:38	MVP transect					